

ANALYSIS OF WRITTEN AND SPOKEN TEXTS IN ENGLISH AND UZBEK

Pazilova Nasibaxon Muhammadqosimovna

Docent, Andijan State foreign languages institute

G'opurova Xusnora Muxsinjon Qizi

Second-year-student of master's degree, Fergana State university

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Abstract. *This article is devoted to problems of written and spoken text which deals with general definitions of text by linguists. It gives information about linguistic features of spoken and written text.*

Keywords: *spoken text, written text, speech, language, linguistic feature, structure, phenomenon.*

АНАЛИЗ ПИСЬМЕННЫХ И РАЗГОВОРНЫХ ТЕКСТОВ НА АНГЛИЙСКОМ И УЗБЕКСКОМ ЯЗЫКАХ

Аннотация. *Данная статья посвящена проблемам письменного и устного текста, в которой рассматриваются общие определения текста лингвистами. Он дает информацию о языковых особенностях устного и письменного текста.*

Ключевые слова: *устный текст, письменный текст, речь, язык, языковая особенность, структура, явление.*

INTRODUCTION

As we know that text is a unit of information exchange and it mainly serves this task. Therefore, its content requires the harmony of tasks such as communication and information exchange. Usually, the text is considered as a two-stage phenomenon of communicative-informational structure. The first of these is the theme-rhema construction of the text, and the second is its substantive (thematic) center or basis. It is customary to study these two features separately, which are considered to be the dynamic (moving) and static (permanent) shells of the text content. In our opinion, the reason for this can be explained by the disproportion of the used research methods. Therefore, if the issue of theme-rhema construction of units above the sentence is studied in relation to the interaction of the parts of these units and the gradual formation of a single whole based on this relation, the phenomenon of the meaningful center is considered in relation to the formed integrated structure - the text. In addition, in most cases, the content center is considered as the same phenomenon as the subject of the text, that is, the name of the main object in the depicted reality, the subject of the message, etc.

REVIEW

The relationship between the content center and the theme-rheme structure has been described unilaterally in English and Uzbek languages: in the description of the content center of the text, importance is given to the thematic aspects of the sentence(s) contained in it, and the aspect of the rheme is left out of consideration. In such a case, it is inevitable that the signs and characteristics of some events related to the construction of the sentence will be directly transferred to the analysis of the text construction. The search for theme-rheme relations in the composition of higher-level structures did not occur by itself. When it is considered as an abstract unit, a template, it is difficult to imagine that its construction will be actual or, in other words, have any meaningful division.

DISCUSSION

The phenomenon of substantive division and theme-rhema relations are characteristic only of communicative structures realized in speech. Therefore, it is better to study this phenomenon and relations from the point of view of text grammar. However, even in the studies conducted in the field of text grammar, there is almost no clear information about the role of theme-rheme relations in the formation of the overall textual content center. In the works of this direction, the main attention is focused on the formation of the content center only with the emergence of thematic relations, and other aspects of the communicative-information structure of the text are left out of consideration. We can see the relationship between theme and rheme in English and Uzbek and the similarities through the following example.

Akmal kitobni ukasiga berdi.

Akhmal gave the book to his brother.

In both sentences, Akmal is the subject, and in Uzbek, he gave the book to his brother, and in the English sentence, gave the book to his brother is the rheme. In addition to this, we would like to mention that in the process of analyzing sentences or texts, we can also see grammatical, lexical, syntactic and stylistic differences in the languages being compared. In our opinion, it is appropriate to analyze the content and semantics of the text in the totality of the factors that ensure its integrity, in the communicative action of the components, that is, at the level of the role of these parts in the formation of the content of the text. The subordination of text-speech units to the goal of fulfilling a common communicative task is the integration of a single step into a content-semantic whole.

Each text has its own content, a specific communicative plan is expressed in it, and it is formed in the process of consciously performed speech creation. A person who engages in speech communication aims at a certain goal and creates his communication plan in relation to this goal. To implement this plan, he appeals to the resources of the language system. A communicative plan is a structure capable of taking the form of a speech message, which has the form of a hidden logical predicate. As A.I. Novikov, who dealt with the problem of text semantics in detail, reminded, the speaker must first have an understanding and an opinion about a certain subject that he wants to convey information about. It is possible that the same idea, as a conceptual structure, forms the substantive center of the text. Of course, the text, like any speech unit, has an appearance and form. In order to feel the harmony of form and content or asymmetric disproportion, it is necessary to perceive it. What should be perceived and understood is the inner form of the text. The inner form forms the content and content of the text. The content of the text is "a structure in thinking, which is formed in the human mind and is not related to the connection of parts (elements) formed by the external form, but to the fact that all linguistic means form a whole." After all, "any linguistic phenomenon loses its ability to express content if it does not have a harmony of form and meaning at the same time, or if the signs of materiality and abstraction-symbolism are not harmonious." [1].

The relationship between the formal and substantive structure of the text is important. When studying this relationship, researchers are based on various research methods and standards. Some of these are methods of analysis in the direction of "pure" linguistics (for example, distributive analysis, direct division into participants), while others are of a functional nature (for example, the method of analysis based on the theory of actual division of speech structures). In recent years, it is known that the methods of psycholinguistic analysis, which require the study of the structure of the text in direct connection with the communication

environment and situation, are becoming widespread. However, regardless of the direction of the used methods, the study of text structure is undoubtedly based on three main criteria.

The criteria for this study are:

- a) character (characteristics) of parts of the structure;
- b) their interaction;
- c) the role of these relationships in the expression of the overall content.

Taking into account these norms leads the researcher's attention to the form and formal structure of the text in any case. N.N. Leontyeva, who is engaged in the research of the content of texts on scientific and technical topics, follows the indicated path and urges to distinguish the linguistic and information transmission aspects of the formation and analysis of the text content. The linguistic approach relies on the analysis of sentence semantics. In other words, the meaning of the text is imagined as a reflection of the semantic structure of individual sentences or as a collection of them. In the second approach, it is taken into account that the transmitted information reflects the content of the entire text. In the content of the information structure, the division of the general meaning structure into the meanings of separate sentences is not taken into account.

Information structures are complex, sufficiently large entities that can take the form of general concepts, concepts. No matter how much N.N. Leontyeva tries to distinguish these two directions from each other, the methods proposed by her regarding the analysis of the text structure are based on the form and formal features of this structure. Approaching the dependence of formal and substantive features of the text in this way (that is, within the framework of the grammar of the text) is nothing more than the realization of the research goal and plan typical of structural-system linguistics. In this case, the syntax of the text is the final stage of the theory of general syntax, because at the same stage, it is possible to study the laws of the construction of structures that are more complex than words and sentences, and to research the principles and rules of speech construction. As a result, the text is placed in the "sentence - word - morpheme - phoneme" sequence, and a place is allocated to it from the highest level.

The inclusion of the text in this line causes it to be given the status of a unit of the language system. In it, the analysis of this phenomenon begins with the interconnection of small units, their interaction in terms of content and form, and ultimately seeks to determine the content of a single integrated "product". We mentioned above that A.I. Novikov suggested that the content of the text should be defined as a semantic structure formed in connection with its communicative purpose and idea in human thinking. But this proposal of a psychologist does not satisfy linguists. First, as the scientist himself admitted, the semantic structure being described should in any case consist of components, but the given definition did not take into account the interaction of its parts. Secondly, the text is not only a product of emotional experiences and actions such as imagination, feeling, perception, but it is a phenomenon that requires the harmony of speech and intellectual actions and is formed in the course of a certain activity. Also, like all linguistic devices, it has internal and external levels, and is a phenomenon that is formed within the framework of the harmony of content and form. As a product of multi-faceted speech thinking activity, it affects the content of its parts. It is true that the content analysis within the text syntax requires, in the first place, to determine the denotation and referent parts of the content, that is, the connection of this content with the reality part. However, it should not be forgotten that a number of communicative-pragmatic features of the content, such as modality,

emotiveness, and temporality (the passage of the event within a certain period of time) are an integral part of the content of the text. In the observations so far, there are cases of not distinguishing between two concepts related to the problem of the content of the text, that is, the concepts of "topic" and "content center".

The reason for not paying attention to the difference of these concepts is the fact that the content of the text or the transmitted information reflects the characteristics of objects and events in reality. But if the topic (theme) is more related to the objective feature or referent of the expressed meaning, then the meaningful center is mainly the idea about the object-phenomenon in reality. One of the main methods used in the denotative-referential approach to the analysis of text content is to identify a set of basic words and phrases that indicate the connection of separate parts of the described reality. Another common method is to separate the main participants of the event, including the "hero" of the narrative. This, in turn, gives the opportunity to choose a title for the text. (This situation can be seen in articles published in the press, school essay topics.) Undoubtedly, the topic is the foundation of the referent situation, and the content begins to form on the basis of this foundation. It is known that denotative and significant layers are distinguished in the content of the text. The denotation of the text is the depicted reality, therefore its content reflects the relationships between the described events and events in many ways. According to psycholinguists, text denotation is a dynamic unit of speech activity, and this unit is reflected in our mind as an image of a certain fragment of reality. The denotative content of the text is understood in the process of perception and understanding of the transmitted information. In order to understand the content and essence of the transmitted information, the student needs to show mental activity and look for evidence [2].

RESULTS

According to A.I. Novikov and G.D. Chistyakova, understanding the text is not limited to linguistic knowledge, it is very important for the information transmitter and receiver to connect its content with a single event in reality. At the same time, it should not be forgotten that the speech image of a single denotation may be different in relation to the idea and intention of the author. According to the authors, "the idea coordinates the beginning and end of the text based on the choice of topics and creates the future text" [3]. Thus, the content of the text is a semantic structure formed in the mind of the author based on the idea, goal and communication environment of the author. The theme of the text is born based on the formation and realization of the author's idea. But the referent situation includes not only objects, but also sign, relational movement. In relation to this, if the denotations in the text are mainly represented by nouns, the relationship between them is determined by means of verbs or other predicates. In order to determine the moral basis that reflects the scope of relations in action, it is better to rely on the description given in relation to the significant relationship, rather than the description of the denotative-referential situation in the nature of subjectivity. The formation of the significant part of the content of the text is also based on the representation of reality (denotation) in speech thinking. But this speech-thinking activity is a second-stage activity, and in its occurrence, in addition to understanding the author's idea and communicative purpose, it is also important to take into account the level of knowledge of the communicators [4]. The interaction of subjective and objective knowledge, individual and general (social) knowledge determines (creates) the content structure of the text. The semantic center of the text or, in other words, its semantic essence is a significant symbol (reflection) between reality and the concept that is born in the

process of speech-thinking perception and the linguistic structure. Such a linguistic and mental-logical connection takes the form of a proposition, and this type of proposition is not only a message about an event, but also a confirmation of the message being conveyed. The concept of a proposition borrowed from the field of predicate logic has been used in linguistics for a long time [5].

In logic, this term is used to name a judgment about reality. That is why in substantive syntax, a proposition is described as a semantic invariant of a series of sentences. For example, sentences such as "Abbas gave me the book", "Will Abbas give me the book?", "Abbas, give me the book!", "Abbas should give me the book" have only one proposition: "Abbas has a book and will give it to me". It can be seen that the semantic and syntactic structure of the proposition corresponds to the structure of the event in reality. But such a structural balance is mainly preserved at the level of the sentence, that is, in the reserve signs of the proposition, i.e., the pattern that provides the linguistic realization of the semantic structure that forms the logical relationship of the reference of the nouns "Abbas", "book" and the pronoun "I" and the predicate "to give" are manifested in its existence. Now, we will see an example of spoken text from artistic works.

— Siz... qochqoqsiz, — dedi.

— Siz...

— Men?

— Siz quvloqsiz.

— Ajab qilaman, — dedi Kumush va shapalog‘i bilan erining yuziga sekingina urib qo‘ydi.

— Bu yoqqa ham...

— U yoqqa Zaynab ursin.

("You... are a fugitive," he said. "You..." "Me?" - You are chaser. "I'm surprised," Kumush said and gently slapped her husband on the face. - This way too... - Let Zaynab hit that side)

(A.Qodiriy, «O‘tkan kunlar»)

From this example we may see the specific features of spoken text that's to say dialogue. In logic, this term is used to name a judgment about reality. That is why in substantive syntax, a proposition is described as a semantic invariant of a series of sentences. For example, sentences such as "Abbas gave me the book", "Will Abbas give me the book?", "Abbas, give me the book!", "Abbas should give me the book" have only one proposition: "Abbas has a book and will give it to me". It can be seen that the semantic and syntactic structure of the proposition corresponds to the structure of the event in reality. But such a structural balance is mainly preserved at the level of the sentence, that is, in the reserve signs of the proposition, i.e., the pattern that provides the linguistic realization of the semantic structure that forms the logical relationship of the reference of the nouns "Abbas", "book" and the pronoun "I" and the predicate "to give". is manifested in its existence.

CONCLUSION

It is known that until now, especially within the framework of the grammar of the text, the main attention was focused on the internal structure of the text and the problems related to the formation of content and meaning of this structure, and now attention is being paid to the content and form of the text. moved to the issue of creation and perception of its content. The

creation of the text and the correct perception of its content are the result of cognitive and speech-cognitive activity. As this activity has a dynamic nature, the text that is its product does not remain in a static state. In order for a certain chain of sentences to become a real text, it needs to be in contact with the person who creates and receives it. Text is created and perceived by humans [6]. A text viewed separately from a person "has no internal energy." It is not enough to enumerate the factors (cohesion, coherence, etc.) that form the unity of the text parts and the factors that make up the whole. The formation of the content of the text is related to the cognitive and communicative ability of the person who creates it. Likewise, the recipient must have this ability. If the cognitive-communicative abilities and opportunities of these two parties are sharply different, the content will be incorrectly perceived, and as a result, the intended communicative goal will not be realized. Thus, the comprehensive analysis of the phenomenon of text content, including the cognitive-communicative direction, is not only of theoretical importance, but also important for the practice of linguistic activity.

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